

DETECTION OF DEFECTS IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES WITH 3D LASER VIBROMETER

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1 Introduction

Reusable Launch Vehicles (RLV) are considered by the European Space Agency (ESA) to guarantee access to space with reduced costs. Various new materials and technologies are considered for construction of RLV's complex components. Cryogenic pressurised structures, such as fuel tanks, are particular interest. It is inevitable that reliable Non-Destructive Inspection (NDI) methods will be required for quality control and maintenance of RLVs. Various NDI methods have been developed over the last fifty years for damage detection in metallic and composite structures. Among them, several techniques have been investigated such as acoustic emission to detect cracks and debonding of cryogenic insulation and delamination for composite structures. Full field investigation with infrared thermography is also interesting but inefficient to detect matrix cracks. Ultrasonic technique is widely used in aeronautic to detect a lot of variety of defects in composite structures. Guided ultrasonic waves for structural damage detection allow scanning large areas [1], [2] and the approach based on non-contact laser vibrometry is particularly attractive [3].

This paper presents the work performed under ESA contract which one of the objectives was to study the capability to detect a wide range of defects by scanning the entire specimen with a 3D Laser acquiring Lamb wave.

2 Test samples design

The first part of the work was to define specimens which should be representative of a reusable cryogenic tank. Because the design of such tank could be complex, the study has been firstly limited in considering a general design based on skin made of composite materials reinforced with stiffeners as shown in Fig 1.

The dimension of curved panel is 300mm×300mm × 1.85 mm. The curvature radius is equal to 2500 mm. The L-shaped welded stiffener is 25mm high and 25mm width. Skin and stiffener are both

AS4/Peek composite materials. The test samples are illustrated in Fig.1. Cryogenic tanks are generally covered by cryogenic insulation which is usually foam material. For this study we have assumed foam is glued on the outer side of the tank. Moreover to prevent leakage, a metallic foil is sometimes added here at the inner side of the tank. linerless cryogenic tank is not actually fully reliable especially when operative pressure or external loads are combined with thermal loads increasing the risk of matrix cracks initiation and propagation during the operation life.

The design office has listed the types of damage to detect to guarantee the health of the tank in the frame of damage tolerance design. So non destructive investigation shall ensure a level of quality in terms of reliability, accessibility and compatibility with the cleanness requirement of cryogenic tank.

In terms of cost objectives, NDI shall be as low as possible.

During the life of the tank, delamination of the composite, debonding of stiffeners and debonding of the cryogenic insulation or even debonding of the liner from composite part are the main events which can cause catastrophic failure.

Delamination of the composite can be due to low velocity impact or due to stress gradient through the thickness due to high thermal gradient. So we have investigated these two configurations with a delaminated zone, generated by drop weight impacts and with delaminated area, generated by the inclusion of a thin foil of Teflon.

Local debonding between the skin and the stiffener has been created with Teflon insert.

Debonding of the cryogenic insulation or of the liner has been created with Teflon insert.

Microcracks of the layers of the skin are generated by thermal fatigue combined with mechanical loads. They may cause leakage or even more the initiation of composite delamination.

Finally, we have considered manufacturing defects (material porosity and welding heterogeneity) which

can also generate composite delamination during the service life.

Microcracks and porosity are illustrated with the micrography in Fig 2.

Fig. 1. Composite specimen: (a) curved panel (b) L-shaped welded stiffener

Fig. 2. Micrography illustrating porosity and microcracks generated by thermal cycling in AS/PEEK composites

3 Rationale of the choice of contactless laser vibrometry

Designers of cryogenic tanks state the following requirements for this study:

- lack of accessibility to the tank which imposes to perform the non destructive investigations via the inner side depending on the manhole dimension,
- no pollution of the inner side of the cryogenic tank which leads to contactless methods,
- reduce time for inspection leads to global methods (optical techniques),
- capability to detect various types of defects,
- high reliability of the detection of the most critical defects.

Ultrasonic waves are particularly efficient to detect all the defects specified by the designers. To meet the constraint of time reduction for inspection, guided ultrasonic waves are attractive and many different damage detection approaches have been developed since the years 90.

The generation and the detection of guided waves can be done with air-coupled sensors such as capacitive sensors or Electromagnetic sensors (EMAT) and various types of laser/optical techniques. Air-coupled transducers have very low sensitivity due to the large acoustic impedance mismatch between air and solid material due to the high attenuation of ultrasound in air.

Laser-based Lamb wave sensing has found relatively less attention in practical applications than Lamb wave generation due to low sensitivity, high noise and high costs. Scanning multi-point laser vibrometers are designed and widely used for vibration measurements, modal analysis and vibration-based damage detection in many areas of engineering applications, predominantly in the frequency domain.

Applications of laser generation and sensing of guided waves as Lamb waves for structural health monitoring of composite structures is not new [4], [5],[6]. Applications of Lamb wave sensing for structural health monitoring are very limited and include damage detection in composite [7] structures. These studies were based only on laser out-of-plane measurements of antisymmetric Lamb wave modes. More recently a three-dimensional (3-D) scanning laser vibrometer was proposed and used for impact damage detection in composite structures [8].The approach allowed for direct out-of-plane and in-plane measurements of Lamb wave responses.

Defects and damage are identified by a change of the response signal in terms of signal attenuation, arrival time and/or mode conversions when fundamental

modes are carefully selected. Because of the anisotropy of composite structures which increases the difficulty of the interpretation of the signals, the basic factors which determine defects and damage detection based on Lamb waves are related to: properties of the structure under inspection, selection of wave propagation modes, transducer selection and location, transducer validation against possible failures, transducer coupling methods and choice of excitation signals [2].

If one of the main advantages with laser is the high speed to control, the main drawbacks are laser light reflectivity requirement of the surface and the potential surface abrasion generated by the laser for generating the waves.

This study has been then focused on the generation of guided waves, the 1st and the 2nd flexural and symmetrical modes with piezosensors and the detection with laser. Even if 1-D laser systems offer higher frequency ranges (not necessarily needed for damage detection in composites), easier to use (simple alignment and focusing) and more cost-effective for an industrial application, 3D laser has been chosen for this study. The full Lamb wave propagation field can be captured to investigate possible wave interactions with most of the defects and damage which can be met in cryogenic tank. Finally this will allow identifying the limitation of 1-D laser technique to detect these defects and damage with these definition of composite structure.

4 Main Features of the experiment

4.1 Generation of Lamb waves

The test samples were instrumented with CeramTec SONOX P5 piezoceramic transducer (diameter 8 mm and thickness 0.2 mm) or PI Instruments PIC 255 transducer (diameter 20 mm and thickness 1 mm) for Lamb wave generation. The transducers were surface-bonded near plate edges. Two different actuator positions, allowing for wave propagation in 0° and 90° directions against fibres, were applied.

Three frequencies (70 kHz, 240 kHz, 500 kHz) with two different amplitude levels (10 and 50 Vp-p) have been applied. This frequency range has covered the fundamental A₀ and S₀ Lamb wave mode propagation.

Examples of Lamb wave dispersion curves for composite materials are given in Fig 3 [9].

Although the S₀ mode is considered as less sensitive to detect damage, a number of research studies have been reported where this mode works better than the

A₀ mode. The other important fact is that the symmetric S₀ mode is faster, (Fig 3), less dispersive and has much lower attenuation than the antisymmetric A₀ mode. This is particularly important in composite materials.

It is also important to note that the energy distribution for various modes is different through the thickness of the plate. This is due to the fact that the in-plane and out-of-plane displacements vary across the thickness. In general, lower modes have more uniform energy distribution than higher modes. However, the S₀ mode has a more uniform distribution than the A₀ mode which exhibits higher levels of energy at the surface.

Fig. 3: Examples of Lamb waves dispersion curves of composite materials, dotted line represents the average frequency range of the sensor (240 kHz)

4.2 Detection of the Lamb waves

Contactless laser vibrometry was used for Lamb wave sensing. A Polytec PSV-400 3-D scanning laser vibrometer was used to scan all investigated specimens. The experimental set-up is shown in Fig 4.

The analysis of data with Polytec PSV-400 3-D allows for five different presentation forms: (1) Lamb wave amplitude responses for given measuring point; (2) 2-D and 3-D animations displaying Lamb wave propagation for the entire scanned area; (3) 2-D and 3-D contour plots of Lamb wave amplitudes for a given wave propagation time (4) cross-sections of 2-D Lamb wave contour plots; (5) 2-D Lamb wave Root Mean Square amplitudes for the entire scanned area. All forms of presentation are possible for the out-of-plane (Z-direction) and in-plane (X- and Y-

direction) measurements. The counterpart of the 3D measurement is time consuming and two hours are necessary to scan the whole specimen with fine mesh grid. 3-D laser scans were very useful for physical understanding of Lamb wave mode propagation. 3-D laser offered better visualization of symmetric modes.

Good quality responses for up to 300 mm wave propagation distances could be achieved when appropriate excitation amplitudes were selected without the need of surface painting of the test samples. Less attenuation was observed for wave propagation in the fiber direction, as expected.

Fig. 4. Experimental set-up used for Lamb wave detection with 3D laser vibrometry.

Fig. 5. Example of the 240 kHz Lamb wave response for the out-of-plane specimen -amplitude contour plot, sample without defects or damage

Fig. 5 illustrates the two modes A0 and S0 in Z direction generates at 240 kHz by the piezo sensor glued nearby the edge of the sample. As it was predicted in Fig 3, the first mode which crosses the

sample is S0 mode. A0 and S0 are well separated in time flight.

5 Damage Detection Results

Laser scanning of Lamb wave responses were successfully achieved for different definitions of test samples and different positions of the Lamb wave emitter glued on the structure. The tests have confirmed all well-known properties of both modes with respect to wave propagation, velocity, and attenuation.

5.1 Porosity detection

Porosity in composite material can be easily detected with ultrasons at high frequency depending on plate thickness. At this frequency range, the signal is well absorbed due to the visco-elasticity behavior of composite material and the two modes A0 and S0 will be mixed together according to Fig 1. Therefore the detection of the porosity is more difficult at 240 kHz as illustrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Detection of porosity –comparison of the amplitude contour plots for 240 kHz Lamb wave propagation in out-of-plane Z direction with C-Scan cartography amplitude at 10 MHz in the same area

5.2 Micro cracks detection

This defect is difficult to detect and needs to have rigorous experimental procedure to enable a reliable comparison with reference samples. Those samples have to give a right estimation of the attenuation scattering with respect to virgin state. We only made a comparison with two samples. Several trials have been performed at 500 kHz which allows detecting small defects. The wavelengths for Lamb wave modes A0 and S0 are respectively 2.7 mm and 7.6 mm. RMS amplitude profiles were analysed across the width of the plate at the area where micro-cracks were expected. The RMS amplitude decay provides some indication about wave attenuation in the analysed components. The amplitude for the in-

plane X direction exhibits similar level of attenuation for both analysed specimens.

However, the results for the in-plane Y and out-of-plane Z directions shows 4 and 7 dB larger level of attenuation, respectively over 100 mm distance for the specimen with micro-cracks.

Further studies with more samples are required to confirm these findings.

Nevertheless it has been shown that A0 Lamb wave can detect composite micro-cracks based on previous studies.

Our investigations were carried out with air coupled sensors on carbon fibre reinforced thermoset resin for different lay-up sequences (Fig. 7.). Cracks are generated by thermal cycling. With this material the cracks generation is easier because the matrix is more brittle at low temperature compared to PEEK matrix.

The measures are in accordance with the experimental results showing cracks density in the ply increases with the increase of its thickness (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. Evolution of the signal (real part of the wave-number k') with thermal fatigue for different lay-up

Fig. 8. Micrographies taken after a) cycle E2, b) cycle E7 for the plate $(0_2/+45_2/90_2/-45_2)_{3s}$

5.3 Delamination detection

Delamination has been simulated by the insertion of a thin Teflon insert of 12 mm square in between two layers during the manufacturing phase.

The presence of the insert can be detected easily with the RMS amplitude analysis for all wave propagation components as seen in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. RMS amplitude contour for 240 kHz 12 mm x 12 mm Teflon insert in composite laminate. a) in-plane X direction, b) in-plane Y direction, c) out of plane Z direction

If this defect is clearly detected, limitation of detection has been found with smaller Teflon inserts positioned at the back side with respect to the scanning surface.

5.4 Impact detection

Damage has been generated with drop weight machine with hemispheric indenter. The energy of the impact is controlled by measuring the speed before the impact. Impact damage is characterized by micro cracks and multiple delamination through the thickness of the structure in the vicinity of the impact. In our case no fiber breakage has been observed.

RMS amplitude analysis reveals the damage which is similar to Teflon insert detection. Fig. 10 illustrates the difficulty encountered with the anisotropy of the wave propagation with composite materials and then the advantage of having advanced data processing of the signal.

Fig. 10. Impact damage detection in the curved composite panel (6 Joules) - RMS amplitude contour plots (upper part) and amplitude profiles across the impacted area (lower part) for 240 kHz Lamb wave propagation in out-of-plane Z direction

The non uniform propagation could hide the defect or damage if the sensor is too close to the area. As it is seen along the line CD, the amplitude of the beam spreading has the same amplitude than the response of the impact which is clearly visible along the line AB.

Out of the propagations lobes, it is possible in the out of plane direction to see the remaining energy in the impact damage and then with the amplitude of the signal to give an order of magnitude of the size of the damage (Fig. 11.).

The damage area is about 14 mm*5 mm for 5 Joules and 18 mm*8 mm for 6 Joules.

Fig. 11. Impact damage detection in the curved composite panel (5 Joules and 6 Joules) - RMS amplitude contour plots (upper part) and amplitude profiles across the impacted area (lower part) for 240 kHz Lamb wave propagation in out-of-plane Z direction

5.5 Stiffener debonding detection

Another point of interest was the detection of local debonding of the stiffener. The experiment consisted to generate the Lamb with the piezo sensor glued on the stiffener. The results in Fig. 12 show how out-of-plane Z component of Lamb wave is guided and attenuated by the stiffener. Wave interaction with 6 mm*12 mm Teflon insert positioned between the skin and the stiffener can be clearly observed in the RMS amplitude contour plot for 240 kHz and RMS amplitude profiles.

5.6 Liner debonding detection

In this case a thin aluminium liner was glued on the skin surface with in the middle the insertion of thin Teflon insert of 12 mm square. The analysis of the RMS amplitude for the 70 kHz excitation in Fig 13

clearly reveals that debonding is much more detected with in-plane wave propagation than out-of-plane direction.

Fig. 12. RMS amplitude contour plots (upper part) and amplitude profile across the width of the specimen (lower part) for 240 kHz Lamb wave propagation (out-of-plane Z direction).

Fig. 13. RMS amplitude contour plot for 70 kHz Lamb wave propagation; a) in-plane X direction, b) out-of-plane Z direction

6 Conclusion

Despite attenuation, wave propagation was possible and as expected, attenuation increases with increasing frequency and less attenuation is observed for wave propagation in fibre direction. Anyway higher frequency excitation is required to detect matrix micro-cracks and porosity as well. Structural features such as stiffeners and cryogenic insulation significantly contribute to increase attenuation level. Moreover, stiffeners act as guides for wave propagation.

The access to in-plane measurements offered by a 3-D Laser was valuable, particularly to physical understanding of wave propagation. Damage detection is more successful when both, i.e. in-plane and out-of-plane components are analysed. Wave propagation animations in the time-domain are very useful to observe wave interaction with damage. S0 mode was better visible in in-plane components.

Amplitude profiles for selected cross-section from Root Mean Square contour plots are particularly useful for damage severity estimation.

The tests performed with guided waves are actually “laboratory studies”.

These tests with 3D Laser have shown the ultra-sonic guided waves techniques have good potentiality to detect small defects or damage size. But these defects can be revealed if the most appropriated ultra-sonic wave (mode, amplitude, frequency range) is generated and detected.

We have noticed that better results are obtained when damage is closer to the surface with respect to the scanning surface. Therefore, small Teflon inserts positioned at the back face are difficult to detect.

If small piezo sensors can generate such waves and could be glued on the external face of the composite, the 3-D scanning laser vibrometer cannot be using at the time being in real conditions with inside access of the tank only. This is because up to now the volume of the three heads of 3-D Laser is not compatible to the size of the access door and the time to control would be too long.

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